

P revention of atherosclerosis: recent recommendations of cardiac societies

Prevención de la aterosclerosis: recomendaciones recientes de las sociedades cardíacas

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Received: 10/20/2024 Accepted: 01/19/2025 Published: 02/12/2025 DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14868436>

Abstract

The article is devoted to the prevention of atherosclerosis based on the latest recommendations of leading cardiological societies. It reviews key risk factors for atherosclerosis, including hypercholesterolaemia, arterial hypertension, diabetes mellitus, obesity and smoking. It emphasises strategic approaches to lifestyle change, such as eating a healthy diet, increasing physical activity, avoiding unhealthy habits and managing stress.

Current approaches to drug prophylaxis, including the use of statins, PCSK9 inhibitors, and drugs to control blood pressure and blood glucose levels, are also analysed. The paper summarises the recommendations of the European Society of Cardiology (ESC), American Heart Association (AHA) and other authoritative organisations, and gives practical advice on how to implement these recommendations in clinical practice.

Key words: atherosclerosis, prevention, cardiological recommendations, risk factors, hypercholesterolemia, rational nutrition, physical activity, vascular health.

Resumen

El artículo está dedicado a la prevención de la aterosclerosis basándose en las últimas recomendaciones de las principales sociedades cardiológicas. Revisa los factores de riesgo clave para la aterosclerosis, incluyendo la hipercolesterolemia, la hipertensión arterial, la diabetes mellitus, la obesidad y el tabaquismo. Hace hincapié en los enfoques estratégicos para el cambio de estilo de vida, como llevar una dieta saludable, aumentar la actividad física, evitar los hábitos no saludables y controlar el estrés.

También se analizan los enfoques actuales para la profilaxis farmacológica, incluido el uso de estatinas, inhibidores de PCSK9 y medicamentos para controlar la presión arterial y los niveles de glucosa en sangre. El artículo resume las recomendaciones de la Sociedad Europea de Cardiología (ESC), la Asociación Estadounidense del Corazón (AHA) y otras organizaciones autorizadas, y ofrece consejos prácticos sobre cómo implementar estas recomendaciones en la práctica clínica.

Palabras clave: aterosclerosis, prevención, recomendaciones cardiológicas, factores de riesgo, hipercolesterolemia, nutrición racional, actividad física, salud vascular.

Atherosclerosis is a major cause of cardiovascular diseases such as coronary heart disease, myocardial infarction and stroke, making it a major cause of mortality and disability worldwide. The disease develops gradually, often remaining asymptomatic until serious complications occur¹. The main risk factors are hypercholesterolaemia, arterial hypertension, diabetes mellitus, obesity, low physical activity and bad habits such as smoking. In recent years, leading cardiology societies, including the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) and the American Heart Association (AHA), have developed updated recommendations for the prevention of atherosclerosis. These include a focus on early diagnosis, lifestyle changes and personalised treatment for high-risk patients. In addition, the introduction of new drugs, such as PCSK9 inhibitors, has opened up additional opportunities to reduce cardiovascular risk.

The aim of the paper is to summarise current approaches to atherosclerosis prevention, analyse the latest international recommendations and propose effective strategies for application in clinical practice.

In the process of writing the study, a study of modern publications, reports and recommendations of leading cardiological societies such as ESC, AHA and ACC (American College of Cardiology) was conducted to identify relevant methods of atherosclerosis prevention. The analysis allows systematising the existing knowledge and identifying directions for further research. Recommendations of different cardiology societies and clinical guidelines were also compared to identify common approaches and differences in atherosclerosis prevention.

In addition, a holistic picture of prevention methods was formed by systematising disparate information from various sources, such as the results of clinical trials, meta-analyses and data from epidemiological studies. Studying the evolution of approaches to atherosclerosis prevention and analysing changes in views on the main risk factors, diagnosis and therapeutic approaches allowed us to understand how scientific progress influences current practice.

Atherosclerosis is a chronic disease in which lipids (mainly cholesterol) and other substances are deposited in arterial walls, leading to the formation of plaques and thickening of vascular walls². The mentioned disease is

one of the main causes of cardiovascular diseases such as myocardial infarction, stroke and chronic heart failure.

Table 1 presents the key risk factors for the development of atherosclerosis.

Table 1. Key risk factors for the development of atherosclerosis

Risk Factor	Description	Preventive measures
Hypercholesterolaemia	Elevated LDL-cholesterol contributes to the formation of atherosclerotic plaques.	Proper diet, physical activity, statins, PCSK9 inhibitors.
Arterial hypertension	High blood pressure damages the endothelium of blood vessels, accelerating inflammation and plaque formation.	Control of blood pressure, reduction of salt intake, drug therapy (ACE inhibitors, etc.).
Diabetes mellitus	Hyperglycaemia damages blood vessels, increases inflammation and impairs lipid metabolism.	Glucose control, proper nutrition, physical activity, sugar-lowering medication.
Obesity	Excess body weight is associated with metabolic disorders and chronic inflammation.	Weight loss, diet, physical activity, reducing saturated fat and sugar intake.
Smoking	Tobacco smoke toxins damage blood vessels, increase inflammation and increase the risk of thrombosis.	Complete smoking cessation.
Age	With age, the risk of vascular damage and the accumulation of atherosclerotic plaques increases.	Early detection of risk factors, preventive screening.
Heredity	Genetic predisposition to dyslipidaemia and cardiovascular disease.	Lipid profile monitoring, preventive treatment in individuals with a family history.
Chronic stress	Increased stress levels	Управление стрессом, релаксация, психотерапия.
Low physical activity	Lack of exercise worsens lipid metabolism and contributes to obesity.	Moderate and regular physical activity (e.g. walking, swimming, running).
Alcohol	Excessive alcohol consumption increases the risk of hypertension and lipid metabolism disorders.	Limiting alcohol consumption.

Hypercholesterolemia is characterised by an increase in the level of low-density lipoproteins (LDL) in the blood, which penetrate the arterial walls, where they are oxidised and provoke inflammation. This circumstance favours the formation of atherosclerotic plaques. LDL-cholesterol is a key element in the process of atherosclerotic plaque formation³. Oxidised forms of LDL activate macrophages, leading to foam cell formation and damage to the vascular wall. Reduction of LDL levels is associated with a significant reduction in the risk of cardiovascular disease.

Sustained high blood pressure increases the load on blood vessels, which leads to their damage and wall thickening. High pressure causes micro-damage to the vascular endothelium, increases lipid penetration into the arterial walls and activates inflammatory processes, which creates favourable conditions for the development of atherosclerosis.

Diabetes mellitus, especially type 2 diabetes, is accompanied by chronically elevated glucose levels, which leads to vascular damage⁴. Hyperglycaemia causes protein glycation, endothelial damage and increased levels of free radicals, which accelerates the process of atherosclerosis. In addition, diabetes is associated with dyslipidaemia (increased triglycerides and decreased HDL levels)⁵.

Overweight, especially visceral obesity, is associated with impaired metabolic processes. Adipose tissue, especially abdominal tissue, actively releases proinflammatory cytokines that contribute to systemic inflammation and insulin resistance, which aggravates dyslipidaemia and hyperglycaemia, increasing atherosclerosis⁶.

Toxic components of tobacco smoke, such as nicotine and carbon monoxide, negatively affect blood vessels. Smoking damages the endothelium, causes vasospasm, increases LDL oxidation and stimulates blood clots. It also lowers levels of HDL, which protect blood vessels from damage.

As we age, the likelihood of atherosclerosis increases significantly due to the accumulation of vascular damage and slower repair processes. Vessels lose elasticity, their walls thicken, and the ability of endothelium to regenerate decreases. These changes contribute to the accumulation of lipids and the formation of atherosclerotic plaques. Genetic predisposition to cardiovascular diseases increases the risk of atherosclerosis⁷. Hereditary factors may be associated with dyslipidaemia (e.g. familial hypercholesterolaemia), metabolic disorders and vascular wall weakness. It is recommended that individuals with a family history of dyslipidaemia should have their lipid profile and other health parameters regularly monitored.

Prolonged exposure to stress increases the risk of cardiovascular disease by activating neurohormonal systems. Stress stimulates the release of cortisol and adrenaline,

which increases blood pressure, increases inflammation and impairs metabolism. Hypodynamia worsens lipid metabolism, contributes to obesity and weakens the cardiovascular system. Lack of regular physical activity lowers HDL levels and increases LDL accumulation in the vascular wall. It also impairs insulin sensitivity and contributes to obesity. These risk factors, both modifiable and non-modifiable, form the basis for the development of preventive and therapeutic strategies to combat atherosclerosis.

A healthy diet plays a crucial role in the prevention of atherosclerosis because it directly affects cholesterol, triglycerides and other key metabolic parameters⁸. It is important to balance macro- and micronutrient intake and to consider the impact of food on vascular health. Key recommendations include increasing consumption of fibre-rich foods such as whole grain products, fruits, vegetables and legumes. These foods help normalise blood cholesterol levels and promote vascular health. You should also limit your intake of saturated fats, which are found in fatty meat products, butter and industrially processed foods. Instead, it is recommended to use unsaturated fats, such as olive oil, flaxseed oil and fish rich in omega-3 fatty acids. An important aspect is to reduce salt intake, which contributes to high blood pressure and increases the load on the cardiovascular system⁹. Nutritionists also advise reducing simple carbohydrates, such as sugar and white flour products, as they contribute to obesity and metabolic disorders.

Increasing physical activity is an integral part of a strategy to prevent atherosclerosis. Regular physical activity improves cardiovascular function, lowers cholesterol, improves insulin sensitivity and maintains a healthy body weight. Moderate physical activity, such as walking, running, swimming or yoga, not only strengthens the heart muscle, but also helps to control blood pressure, blood glucose levels and reduces inflammation in the body. To achieve a preventive effect, it is recommended to engage in at least 150 minutes of moderate-intensity or 75 minutes of vigorous-intensity physical activity per week.

Quitting bad habits such as smoking and excessive alcohol consumption is key to preventing atherosclerosis. Smoking is one of the main factors contributing to the development of atherosclerosis because it damages the vascular walls, increases LDL oxidation and promotes blood clot formation¹⁰. Complete smoking cessation significantly reduces the risk of cardiovascular disease and improves vascular health. Excessive alcohol consumption is also associated with increased blood pressure, cholesterol levels and the development of obesity. Limiting or eliminating alcohol altogether helps reduce the risks associated with atherosclerosis.

Stress management plays an important role in the prevention of atherosclerosis because chronic stress can increase cortisol and adrenaline levels, which in turn causes vasoconstriction, increased blood pressure, and

accelerated inflammation in the body. Regular use of stress reduction techniques such as meditation, deep breathing, relaxation, and physical activity significantly reduces the effects of stress on the cardiovascular system. Psychological support and stress management techniques can significantly improve quality of life and reduce the risk of atherosclerosis¹¹.

Modern approaches to drug prevention of atherosclerosis include the use of various classes of drugs aimed at controlling the main risk factors of the disease, such as hypercholesterolemia, arterial hypertension and diabetes mellitus. Effective use of these drugs helps to significantly reduce the likelihood of developing atherosclerotic diseases such as coronary heart disease, myocardial infarction and stroke.

PCSK9 inhibitors are a relatively new class of drugs that are used to lower cholesterol levels, especially in patients who have not reached target values with statins or who cannot tolerate them. Drugs such as alirocumab and everocumab block the PCSK9 protein, which promotes the destruction of LDL receptors in the liver. This increases the number of receptors on liver cells, which in turn increases the utilisation of LDL from the blood and reduces its levels. PCSK9 inhibitors have shown high efficacy in reducing cholesterol levels and cardiovascular disease risk and are becoming an important addition to conventional treatment strategies¹².

Blood pressure medication also plays a key role in the prevention of atherosclerosis. Treatment of arterial hypertension helps to reduce the burden on blood vessels, decreases the likelihood of vascular damage and reduces the risk of stroke, myocardial infarction and other vascular diseases. The main classes of drugs used to control blood pressure include angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors, angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs), diuretics, beta-blockers, and calcium antagonists. These drugs help to relax blood vessels, improve their patency and lower blood pressure. Systematic treatment of hypertension significantly reduces the risk of atherosclerosis.

Blood glucose control medications such as metformin, insulin and drugs belonging to the group of SGLT2 inhibitors also play an important role in the prevention of atherosclerosis in patients with diabetes mellitus. Elevated blood glucose levels promote insulin resistance and accelerate the process of atherogenesis, so glycaemic control is key to preventing cardiovascular disease. Metformin, which is the main drug for the treatment of type 2 diabetes, helps to normalise blood sugar levels and reduce inflammation in the body. In addition to controlling glucose levels, SGLT2 inhibitors also have vasoprotective and cardioprotective effects, reducing the risk of cardiovascular disease among diabetics¹³.

Thus, modern approaches to medication prevention of atherosclerosis include the complex use of drugs to control cholesterol, blood pressure and blood glucose

levels. The combined approach, taking into account individual risk factors, can significantly reduce the likelihood of atherosclerosis and related complications.

Discussion

Recommendations of the European Society of Cardiology (ESC), American Heart Association (AHA) and other authoritative organisations on the prevention of atherosclerosis are based on current data on the development of cardiovascular disease (CVD) and risk reduction strategies. Such recommendations include a comprehensive approach aimed at lifestyle modification, drug therapy and monitoring of risk factors.

The European Society of Cardiology (ESC) in its latest guidelines emphasises early diagnosis and comprehensive prevention of cardiovascular diseases, including atherosclerosis.

The ESC recommends using the SCORE (Systematic COronary Risk Evaluation) scale to determine the 10-year risk of developing cardiovascular disease based on risk factors such as age, sex, blood pressure, smoking and cholesterol levels. For patients at high and very high risk, more aggressive preventive measures are recommended.

It is important to reduce your intake of saturated fats, salt and sugar. It is also recommended to increase the intake of vegetables, fruit, whole-grain products and fish. Controlling body weight, preventing obesity and maintaining a normal body mass index (BMI) are important measures¹⁴.

The ESC recommends regular moderate physical activity such as walking, swimming or running for at least 150 minutes per week, which helps to reduce the risk of atherosclerosis and improve overall cardiovascular health.

Patients at high risk of cardiovascular disease are prescribed cholesterol-lowering medications (e.g. statins), blood pressure control medications, and medications to improve glucose control in diabetic patients. The ESC recommends complete smoking cessation and limiting alcohol consumption to improve cardiovascular health.

The American Heart Association (AHA) follows similar recommendations to the ESC, but with some specific aspects aimed at the American population. This association uses the ASCVD (atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease) scale, which assesses the 10-year risk of developing atherosclerosis and cardiovascular disease. This helps to choose a prevention strategy, including drug therapy to lower cholesterol and control blood pressure¹⁵.

The American Heart Association recommends prescribing statins to patients at high risk of atherosclerosis, including those with pre-existing cardiovascular disease, as well as patients with hypercholesterolaemia and diabetes. Statins reduce LDL levels and have an additional protective effect on blood vessels.

The AHA emphasises achieving and maintaining normal blood pressure levels (less than 130/80 mmHg) in all adults. ACE inhibitors, angiotensin receptor blockers, diuretics and beta-blockers are used for this purpose. The AHA guidelines emphasise the need for glucose control in patients with type 2 diabetes to prevent vascular complications. The use of metformin and insulin, as well as newer drugs such as SGLT2 inhibitors, are recommended to treat diabetes and improve cardiovascular health.

The AHA emphasises a healthy lifestyle, including eating a healthy diet (reducing saturated fat intake, increasing fibre intake), physical activity, smoking cessation and moderate alcohol consumption. The AHA also recommends regular cholesterol and blood pressure checks in adults over age 20.

WHO emphasises global strategies to control cardiovascular disease, including prevention of atherosclerosis. The organisation recommends improved nutrition, increased physical activity, smoking cessation and control of risk factors such as arterial hypertension and diabetes mellitus. WHO also supports global initiatives to reduce salt and sugar intake. The NHS focuses on strategies to prevent atherosclerosis through lifestyle modification and early intervention. The prevention programme includes regular cholesterol and blood pressure checks, as well as recommendations to improve diet, increase physical activity and reduce stress¹⁶.

All these recommendations agree that prevention of atherosclerosis requires a comprehensive approach, including proper nutrition, physical activity, drug therapy and avoidance of bad habits. Each organisation emphasises the importance of early diagnosis and an individual approach to treatment, taking into account risk factors, which can significantly reduce the likelihood of cardiovascular disease and improve the quality of life of patients.

The implementation of recommendations on atherosclerosis prevention in clinical practice requires a comprehensive approach, including both lifestyle changes and drug therapy¹⁷. Physicians need not only to be informed about the latest recommendations of cardiological societies, but also to adapt them to specific patients, taking into account their individual characteristics. Here are some practical tips for implementing these recommendations into clinical practice.

For effective prevention of atherosclerosis, it is important to assess a patient's cardiovascular risk in a timely and accurate manner. The use of scales such as SCORE (ESC) or ASCVD (AHA) helps physicians to predict the risk of atherosclerotic disease.

Prevention and treatment of hypertension are key measures to reduce the risk of atherosclerosis. It is important to closely monitor blood pressure and, if necessary, adjust treatment with antihypertensive drugs. For patients with hypertension, the target blood pressure level is less than 130/80 mm Hg.

Art. It is important to regularly monitor blood pressure during treatment and, if necessary, adjust therapy (ACE inhibitors, angiotensin receptor blockers, diuretics, etc.), and also teach patients methods of self-monitoring blood pressure at home.

Prevention and treatment of arterial hypertension are key measures to reduce the risk of atherosclerosis. It is important to carefully monitor blood pressure and adjust treatment with antihypertensive medication if necessary. For patients with arterial hypertension, the target blood pressure level is less than 130/80 mmHg. It is important to regularly monitor blood pressure during admission and, if necessary, adjust therapy (ACE inhibitors, angiotensin receptor blockers, diuretics, etc.), as well as educate patients in methods of self-monitoring of blood pressure at home.

Patients with high LDL cholesterol levels or high risk of cardiovascular disease are recommended to take statins and, if necessary, PCSK9 inhibitors. Such drugs not only reduce cholesterol levels but also have a protective effect on blood vessels¹⁸. Statins are prescribed to all patients at high or very high risk of cardiovascular disease and to patients with hypercholesterolaemia. It is important to start with low doses and gradually increase the dose if necessary to reach the target cholesterol level (less than 1.8 mmol/L for LDL). It is also important to discuss with patients the possible side effects of statins and treatment options if they occur.

For patients with type 2 diabetes, glucose control and control of insulin resistance play an important role in the prevention of atherosclerosis. Drugs such as metformin as well as newer drugs such as SGLT2 inhibitors are used for this purpose.

Blood glucose and HbA1c levels should be checked regularly in diabetic patients. Use metformin as a first-line treatment to improve blood sugar control and consider adding SGLT2 inhibitors to improve cardiovascular prognosis in high-risk patients.

One of the most important components of atherosclerosis prevention is lifestyle changes. Doctors should actively recommend to patients a healthy diet, regular physical activity, smoking cessation and moderate alcohol consumption. We need to start with simple recommendations for lifestyle changes. It is important to educate patients about nutrition, emphasising the importance of reducing saturated fat and salt intake and increasing fibre intake. Patients should be encouraged to engage in at least 150 minutes of moderate physical

activity per week and reminded to stop smoking and limit alcohol consumption¹⁹.

Stress management and the psycho-emotional state of the patient are important in the prevention of atherosclerosis. Incorporating relaxation and stress management techniques into clinical practice can significantly improve the patient's condition. Recommendations for stress reduction, such as meditation, yoga and breathing exercises, should be included in the treatment programme and consideration should be given to referring patients for counselling with a psychologist or psychotherapist if stress and depression contribute significantly to the deterioration of health status.

Prevention of atherosclerosis requires regular monitoring of the patient's condition in order to timely adjust treatment and prevent the development of complications. In this regard, it is important to organise regular check-ups to monitor cholesterol levels, blood pressure and other indicators in patients at increased risk of atherosclerosis, which will allow timely correction of treatment and maintain the patient's health at an optimal level.

Prevention of atherosclerosis requires the collaboration of different specialists such as cardiologists, endocrinologists, nutritionists and psychologists to provide comprehensive care to patients. For this reason, it is necessary to establish a team of specialists who will work with patients on different aspects of atherosclerosis prevention: cardiologists to prescribe drug therapy, dieticians to develop a nutritional plan, trainers and physiotherapists to organise physical activity, and psychologists to work with the patient's emotional state²⁰.

Implementation of recommendations on atherosclerosis prevention into clinical practice requires integration of scientific data into everyday work with patients. Physicians should actively apply the principles of a personalised approach aimed at improving quality of life and reducing cardiovascular risks in patients. It is important not only to prescribe drug treatment, but also to actively work with patients to change their lifestyle, which, in turn, contributes to the effectiveness of prevention and treatment of atherosclerosis.

Prevention of atherosclerosis requires a comprehensive and integrated approach, including lifestyle changes, drug therapy, and regular monitoring of risk factors. This approach involves not only the impact on cholesterol, blood pressure and blood glucose levels, but also the prevention of such factors as smoking, obesity and stress, which contribute to the development of the disease.

Drugs such as statins, PCSK9 inhibitors and antihypertensives play a key role in the drug prevention of atherosclerosis. They help control cholesterol, blood pressure and blood glucose levels, reducing the risk of cardiovascular disease. Timely use of these drugs is especially important for high-risk patients.

Recent recommendations from the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) and the American Heart Association (AHA) emphasise the need for early diagnosis and prevention of atherosclerosis and the use of risk scales to determine intervention strategies. Cardiological societies insist on the active use of drug therapy and lifestyle changes to reduce cardiovascular risks.

Lifestyle changes remain the main focus of atherosclerosis prevention. A healthy diet, regular physical activity, smoking cessation and moderate alcohol consumption are the main components of effective prevention. It is important for physicians to actively educate patients on the principles of a healthy lifestyle, as well as to regularly monitor their health status to prevent the development of the disease.

Effective prevention of atherosclerosis requires the participation of various specialists: cardiologists, endocrinologists, nutritionists, trainers and psychologists. Only coordinated actions of all participants in the process can lead to successful reduction of risk factors and prevention of cardiovascular diseases. The introduction of modern methods of atherosclerosis prevention contributes to the reduction of morbidity and mortality from cardiovascular diseases, which in turn reduces the economic burden of health care and improves public health in general. It is important that prevention of atherosclerosis becomes not only the responsibility of medical professionals, but also part of the general public consciousness.

Thus, prevention of atherosclerosis is a multifaceted task that requires an active and involved approach on the part of both medical specialists and patients themselves. Correct diagnosis, timely use of drug therapy, as well as lifestyle changes are important steps on the way to a healthy and long life free from the consequences of atherosclerosis.

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